

ECONOMIC SCIENCES

THE IMPORTANCE OF E-COMMERCE IN HEALTHCARE

Ahmadova T.

*PhD student, Institute of Economics of the Ministry of Science and Education,
Azerbaijan, Baku*

Abstract

The aim of the study is to explore the theoretical and conceptual foundations of the implementation of e-commerce in health care. The methodology of the study consists of theoretical views and conceptual and methodological approaches derived from foreign scientific research conducted in the relevant direction. The practical significance of the research lies in the fact that the findings can be applied to the implementation of e-commerce in the healthcare sector. The results of the study are related to the assessment of the role of e-commerce in improving the quality of medical services and their more effective organization, as well as the adoption of more effective measures to intensify the development of the health sector. The originality and scientific novelty of the study lies in the identification of theoretical and methodological approaches to the role of e-commerce in the effective organization of medical services in a global digital transformation.

Keywords: e-business in healthcare, e-commerce in healthcare, e-health, digital health.

Introduction.

Today's health care sector has become one of the largest and most dynamic industries in terms of job creation, innovation, and spending. Impressive advances have been made in improving the quality of public health, life expectancy, and universal convergence. However, there are always questions about the scarcity of resources and how to use them, how to improve the equity, efficiency, and effectiveness of health care services. E-commerce is a great solution for health care because it uses limited resources in the most efficient way that can support the health of the nation.

In recent years, the Internet has become the new trusted interactive channel with all the capabilities to build remote self-service and closer relationships between business partners. Offering global reach, being highly interactive, it enables real-time response to consumer requests around the world. While the adoption of the Internet in the healthcare sector is possible, it has been slow, very slow compared to other industries. While there are technological challenges, as well as a strong increase in the role of human relationships, institutional barriers are commonly cited as the main reason for the slow adoption of the Internet. The new networked health care environment and eHealth are transforming the practice of medicine into an informative, patient-centered, and responsive global marketplace. It has also already changed the balance of power between players in the healthcare sector (consumers, healthcare providers, pharmaceutical companies, medical device manufacturers and suppliers, carriers, technology integrators, insurance companies, etc.), changing the way things work for the entire spectrum of participants.

E-business in healthcare.

E-business is not just an electronic version of business or the application of new technologies to old structures and processes. E-business is understood as a global concept that includes all internal and external

business processes of an organization, aimed at facilitating relationships between businesses and partners by integrating and synchronizing the necessary electronic tools [3]. The benefits of e-business are lower costs of operating in the marketplace (transaction costs), particularly lower process costs, and improved knowledge sharing.

E-business, which supports all (business) company processes by providing electronic tools to implement those processes, is considered a common approach regardless of the field. In principle, the term can be used for all e-supported processes in any type of healthcare business, from medical professionals to manufacturers in the healthcare industry. However, e-business is rarely understood in this way in health care because there are other terms, such as telemedicine, that unambiguously refer to electronic communication processes between health care providers and between health care providers and patients. With the development of the Internet, the term eHealth has emerged. It bears some resemblance to the term e-business. eHealth is the process of providing health care through electronic means, either related to business or solely to patient care. One of the prevailing definitions extends eHealth to the convergence of medical informatics, public health, and business. E-business in healthcare is a subset of eHealth that encompasses the business domain. Thus, all e-supported health care delivery processes emanating from business management, as well as all supply and production processes in health care, are defined as eHealth business [3]. Figure 1. shows the relationship between e-health, e-business, and e-business in health care. E-business in health care is a component of e-health and applies e-business methods and tools to the health care market with its specific characteristics.

Figure 1. Relationship between e-business and e-health

What is usually understood by the name of business processes depends on the type of enterprise or health care organization, because business processes describe the activities of the enterprise. In terms of health care providers, the core business is patient care; in the case of teaching hospitals, it is education and training and research and development. To distinguish e-business in health care from e-health, e-business in health care refers to issues related to referrals, patient care, education and training, and research and development. It includes all functions and processes related to management, such as accounting and finance, controls, purchasing, logistics (including materials management), marketing, asset and facility management, and human resource management. From the supplier's perspective, all supply-related processes are included in the business domain. Finally, from a payer perspective, all business processes related to the use of electronic resources are included in e-business in healthcare. Almost every type of business process or business relationship in health care can be supported electronically. As with e-business in general, the distinction between different customers, purchasers or recipients and providers or suppliers provides good insight into the various stakeholders and their interactions. However, it

needs to be complemented by health care providers, payers (insurance companies, health maintenance organizations, health coffers, government programs, national health service, etc.) and some specifications [3].

If e-health covers all electronic interactions in health care, e-business in health care is a subset of it and therefore is understood more narrowly than e-business in general. Thus, e-supported processes originating from the field of business management are denoted as e-business in health care. Here, the flow of clinical information between healthcare providers themselves, as well as between patients and healthcare providers in the context of patient admission, treatment/care, discharge, and transfer is explicitly excluded in e-business in healthcare. Figure 2. presents a matrix of relationships between e-business participants in health care. Any of the cells in the table can be listed as an eHealth business. Some of the cells already have defined use cases, while others have pilot or still experimental applications. Overall, because the field is highly innovative and new business models are being created, it is expected that new scenarios will emerge in the future that will fill many, if not all, of the cells in the matrix.

		Customer/Buyer/Recipient				
		Consumer/ Citizen/ Patient	Business	Government (in general)	Payers	Healthcare Provider
Supplier/ Provider	Consumer/ Citizen/ Patient	C2C	C2B mail-ordering patient appliances	C2G	C2P general inquiries	C2H online pharmacy
	Business	B2C mail-ordering patient appliances	B2B supply chain	B2G	B2P	B2H supply chain
	Government (in general)	G2C information	G2B about	G2G new	G2P regulations	G2H and acts
	Payers	P2C reimbursements	P2B	P2G	P2P reimburse- ments	P2H claim management
	Healthcare provider	H2C marketing	H2B supply chain	H2G	H2P claim management	H2H marketing

Figure 2. Customer/supplier matrix of eBusiness in healthcare

In conclusion, e-business in healthcare is defined as the totality of all electronically supported processes designed to exchange business information in healthcare between one or more customers/buyers/recipients and their suppliers/providers. Among the more established use cases are all bi-directional and multi-directional communication processes of healthcare providers with product and service providers (H2B/B2H) as well as between the providers themselves (B2B) and healthcare providers (H2H) who collaborate on the same business scheme. In health care e-business, examples of the use of procurement (H2B) and sales (B2H and B2B) have developed over the past few years that illustrate e-business principles well. This is consistent with similar developments in e-business in general, where e-procurement is one of the best known and most studied applications of e-business. It should be noted that according to healthcare marketplace customs, the provider side is understood as e-procurement (online purchasing) and the supplier side is understood as e-commerce (online sales) [3].

In no other sector than healthcare, products are bought by process owners (healthcare workers). Therefore, the technical and organizational procedures of e-business in healthcare must take the knowledge factor into account when automating the supply chain. E-business in healthcare is special because healthcare is special and requires a collaborative effort among stakeholders to gain momentum.

The role of e-commerce in healthcare.

E-commerce refers to the process of purchasing and selling goods, services, and information through computer networks. It merges business operations with electronic infrastructures, enabling traditional transactions to occur digitally, unconstrained by physical or geographical barriers. The current utilization of e-commerce within the healthcare sector is broad, indicating its potential to support the industry's restructuring endeavors [1, 5]. Global Market Insights, an analyst firm, forecasts a significant compound annual growth rate (CAGR) of 28.5% for the digital health market from 2020 to 2026. With the increasing availability of the internet and popularity of mobile/internet applications, e-commerce is creating new opportunities for the healthcare sector, especially in telemedicine and telepharmacy, unlocking previously untapped potential and becoming an important aspect of online retail [9].

Rapid advances in technology have led to increased consumer expectations regarding the quality of health care. Hospitals, clinics and other health care providers are forced to meet these expectations efficiently and cost-effectively. E-commerce can have a significant impact on the cost, efficiency and quality of overall health care management and delivery [5]. Achieving efficiency in health care involves the use of information technology, and especially the Internet [4]. With appropriate e-commerce business models set up and implemented appropriately, the goal of effectively managing health care at a lower cost will be achieved. Adopting e-commerce strategies allows health care providers to operate more efficiently, especially those using outdated paper-based systems. As a result, hospitals and physicians can review a patient's entire medical history

and make the correct diagnosis, saving the patient a lot of time [5].

Demand in the global healthcare e-commerce market is growing due to the continued development of the e-commerce industry and online drug sales. As consumers turn to the Internet for their medical needs, e-commerce vendors have opened up a new segment for healthcare. The healthcare e-commerce market is striving for maturity, and some medical products are being dispersed through e-commerce channels. Therefore, total revenues in the global healthcare e-commerce market are expected to grow in the coming years. Investment in the e-commerce industry has trickled down to online sales of medical products. The lucrative opportunities in the global healthcare e-commerce market have prompted prominent venture capitalists to place big bets on this market. This trend has given a strong boost to the growth graph of vendors operating in the global healthcare e-commerce market. The next decade is expected to bring new opportunities for online vendors in the healthcare marketplace. This prediction is based on the development of a robust verification system for online health care products [10]. The healthcare industry has become a multifaceted field, with sales and purchases being made through multiple channels. Online sales channels have become the most popular option among consumers, and this trend has contributed to the growth of the global healthcare e-commerce marketplace.

E-commerce is revolutionizing the landscape of healthcare, offering unprecedented opportunities when combined with advanced technology. While healthcare traditionally performs well in its conventional roles, the integration of technology propels it to surpass many leading industries. Several prominent trends in e-commerce are currently shaping the realm of e-health:

- *Artificial Intelligence (AI)*: The healthcare AI market is poised to reach a remarkable \$36.1 billion by 2025. AI has revolutionized online commerce by enhancing efficiency and reducing human error. Its applications in healthcare e-commerce are vast, spanning early diagnosis, patient care, medication distribution, health research, surgery, virtual support, and prescriptions.

- *Blockchain*: Approximately one in five medical and healthcare businesses utilize blockchain for managing patient information and identity, as per an IDC report. Forecasts by BIS Research suggest that blockchain technology will be commercially employed in 55% of all healthcare applications by 2025, propelling its share of the healthcare market to \$5.61 billion from \$170 million.

- *Omnichannel*: Multichannel healthcare offers a seamless consumer experience across various online technologies. Customers can access services through a multitude of devices, including smartphones, computers, and tablets, or even through physical stores. Multichannel healthcare is expected to become a prominent trend in medical e-commerce.

- *Augmented Reality (AR) and Virtual Reality (VR)*: Global investment in AR and VR in healthcare is projected to reach \$5.1 billion by 2025. Virtual reality has emerged as a dominant trend in the online

healthcare market, with businesses of all sizes investing in its potential to revolutionize healthcare delivery [9].

Because e-commerce has not been utilized to its full/maximum potential because people have not been able to completely let go of tradition and embrace new technology. The key to success lies first and foremost in the full participation of consumers and health care providers [5]. Research into the factors that help gain consumer confidence in e-commerce in the healthcare sector has been an ongoing focus of researchers. A survey of 200 people between the ages of 18 and 60 showed how consumers perceive the importance of some selected factors in making them feel safe when shopping online. Based on the survey, the following can be noted:

- 62% of respondents have a positive attitude toward purchasing drugs and medical services online.
- The majority of respondents, i.e. 69.5%, have experience buying medicines online. The majority of respondents who have experience buying medicines online make purchases rarely, and only a few buy medicines every month. The remaining 30.5% never shop online and therefore have no experience.
- 66% of respondents believe it is very important to create new opportunities through an e-commerce platform to change the traditional way of the healthcare sector.
- For 73% of respondents, it is very important to know how protected their personal information is when receiving an online consultation.
- 67.5% of the respondents strongly agreed that e-commerce presents enough opportunities for the healthcare sector. These results strongly suggest that e-commerce represents a significant opportunity for the healthcare industry.
- 40% of respondents prefer to purchase services related to counseling, diagnostics, medicine, etc., on one platform.
- Reputation and recommendations (e.g., media, family, friends, etc.) are important for 39% of respondents to promote e-commerce and inform people in the healthcare sector.
- 47% of respondents found it very important to provide the best healthcare sector services on an e-commerce platform to attract patients.
- For 60% of the respondents, favorable price and offer are very important factors in using online services, etc. [10]

The results of the survey suggest that e-commerce has a lot to offer the healthcare sector. With the rapid spread of the Internet and mobile applications, the prospects for health care through e-commerce are increasing. However, given that the primary user interface is the browser, there are still pressing concerns about security, patient privacy, and technology costs [10].

E-commerce covers both classic business-to-business (B2B) and business-to-consumer (B2C) relationships. Among the many different technical and organizational approaches for connecting business partners, electronic trading platforms play an important role. They are either forums - understood literally - for presenting goods and negotiating prices, or they act as technical hubs for communication and applications [3].

Healthcare: B2B - includes transactions and information exchange between providers, hospitals, insurance agencies, state regulatory agencies and physicians' offices. Patients - the end users - are not directly involved [1].

The main emphasis in B2B e-commerce is on the supply chain. B2B seeks to achieve three goals: improve efficiency, reduce transaction costs, and provide real-time information to all stakeholders. Efficiency tends to be improved by simplifying the delivery of healthcare services. Multi-level approvals are being eliminated and replaced by simpler and faster approvals using artificial intelligence technologies. Inventories are better managed and tracked by centralizing their placement and sharing information about usage and future needs. Proactive disease management and implementation of preventive health measures helps avoid long hospital stays. Transaction costs are reduced by reducing the cost of placing purchase orders with suppliers, reducing the cost of paying for goods and services, and reducing the cost of communicating vital information. All of this is usually accomplished by combining requests from different departments or groups for quantity discounts, getting up-to-date pricing information, and using the Internet to process all transactions. Real-time information provides status reports such as hospital utilization, treatment tracking, and review of information exchanged. Reporting is achieved by optimizing all communication standards, connecting all participants in the health care system through the Internet backbone, and actively sharing information [1].

Healthcare: B2C - is an electronic marketplace designed to inform healthcare users about healthcare products and services. The ultimate goal of B2C e-commerce is either to save future healthcare costs by better informing users, or to make a profit by selling products and services. To achieve its goals, B2C e-commerce relies on creating attractive sites with easy-to-follow purchase transactions, organizing electronic discussion forums or chat groups, and providing privacy features to protect against identity theft. The goal of these efforts is to increase customer satisfaction, improve customer service and reduce health care costs. Some healthcare providers are using the B2C platform as a means of building brand loyalty by building relationships with patients, developing new markets online and gathering information about consumers' buying habits. They are winning over consumers who rely on the Internet as their primary source of healthcare information. Health care providers are also joining the Internet and making health care products available directly to consumers [1].

Unfortunately, in practice, B2C healthcare providers face a number of obstacles. These obstacles include regulatory and legal challenges, high costs, limited access to capital, consumer resistance, price transparency, difficulty managing multiple providers, etc. In practice, all of the above means that innovation in health care delivery (e.g., from face-to-face to digital) has been incredibly slow. While pharmaceutical and other companies are innovating in health care, the system that provides them to patients is developing very slowly [6].

Healthcare: G2C - is an expression of the reciprocal relationship between citizens and government and includes several electronic services (e-services), such as issuing birth certificates, providing medical information. Electronic health services (e-health) provided

to citizens are among the services to which a special approach is applied. E-health is seen as an important sector that is developing at the intersection of medical informatics, medicine, and business.

E-health refers to such medical services and information, which contribute to the formation of new information relations between patients and medical specialists by expanding with the help of the Internet and technology, increasing efficiency and quality. In practice, e-health applications can include the following:

- Electronic health records;
- Electronic health cards;
- Electronic prescription service;
- Medical information network;
- Telemedicine services;
- Portable systems;
- Portals specializing in health care [2].

Along with these, several other ICT tools can be mentioned for disease prevention, diagnosis, health monitoring, and quality of life management. At the same time, e-health services are associated with medical experts or medical staff as G2C services. Citizens' expectations of e-health services, such as the availability of best practices and useful information, improved quality of medical services, new treatments, long-term medical support, and health insurance, are now expanding.

It is no exaggeration to say that the pandemic changed the face of commerce. As businesses got creative, shoppers tried ways to shop that were completely new to them. Many are now accustomed to a wide range of these shopping innovations. In the past two years, 68% of shoppers have purchased goods in new ways. Consumption of new services is occurring at an astonishingly fast pace. For example, between 2020 and 2022, the percentage of shoppers who will use a pickup service has nearly doubled, from 31% to 60%. Remarkably, the use of these new technologies and services doesn't seem to be limited to the era of social distance. In three years, an overwhelming majority expects their use to remain the same or increase. 61% of shoppers who shop through social media expect to do so more in three years [7]. And also, 69% of customers want new ways to get existing products and services. In turn, companies have accelerated investments in digital technology to meet online demand. Healthcare and life sciences are no exception. Today's healthcare consumers are comfortable using digital versions of traditionally face-to-face services, from remote monitoring to virtual checkups and more. Increasingly, digitally empowered consumers are taking matters into their own hands. Nearly three-quarters of consumers - 11 percentage points more than in 2019 - are taking charge of their health management by reaching out to various parties (e.g., primary care physicians, specialists, insurers). To facilitate health management through different parties, organizations are investing in integrated care and connected physician and clinician expertise [8].

Conclusions.

The goal and primary objective of medicine and the health care sector is to find the most innovative and cost-effective way to treat disease while maintaining

high standards of care. The school of medicine presupposes specialized knowledge, skills, experience. E-commerce is the ideal medical tool to achieve this goal of medicine. As healthcare costs continue to rise around the world, e-commerce plays an important role in improving the quality, efficiency, effectiveness, and affordability of healthcare services in the most cost-effective way possible.

Although eHealth has its pros and cons (reliance on very sensitive and personal information stored and controlled electronically online), if eCommerce is deployed correctly with strategic IT planning and IT infrastructure, it will not only save time and costs, but also increase efficiency and productivity between patients, physicians, and healthcare providers. Thanks to the large number of companies specializing in data systems and computer software platforms, e-commerce can be done in a secure and highly efficient manner. And this proves that, in the future, no market player who wants to remain competitive will be able to avoid implementing modern web-based procurement, distribution and logistics processes to survive in an increasingly competitive world.

References

1. Aggarwall A.K., Travers S. E-Commerce in healthcare: changing the traditional landscape. *Journal of Healthcare Information Management*, 2001, vol. 15, no. 1, 25-34.
2. Aliguliyev R., Yusifov F. Electronic Health as a component of G2C services. *International Journal of Advanced Computer Science and Applications (IJACSA)*, 2017, vol. 8, no. 3, 201-206.
3. Hubner U., Elmhorst M.A. *eBusiness in healthcare: from eProcurement to Supply Chain Management*. Springer-Verlag London Limited 2008.
4. Kearns E.H., Holmes S.C., Schmidt G. The role of e-Commerce in healthcare. *Clinical report, Science Business and Education Inc., Spokane, WA, U.S.A. CLMA/ASCP, New Orleans, LA, June 26-29, 2002.*
5. Lok Chee L.F., Yazdanifard R. Ecommerce's important role in the medical sector. *2011 International Conference in Information Communication and Management, IPCSIT*, vol. 16, 15-22. IACSIT Press, Singapore, 2011.
6. Ryan M. B2C Healthcare – full description. Full on eCommerce, 2022. www.fullonecommerce.com/b2c-healthcare-full-description.html
7. Salesforce Research. *State of the connected customer (5th edition)*, 2022. www.salesforce.com
8. Salesforce Research. *Trust in a new era of health. Second edition connected health consumer*, 2021. www.salesforce.com
9. Shah K. *Everything you need to know about healthcare e-Commerce*. Magento Association, 2022. www.magentoassociation.org/commerce-co-op/full-article/everything-you-need-to-know-about-health-care-e-commerce
10. Yadav A., Gupta A., Naseem A., Dwivedi A., A study on e-Commerce health care services and their role on health sector. *International Journal of Research Publication and Reviews*, 2022, vol. 3, no. 7, 2520-2552.